

I. Introduction

The purpose of this Consultation technical report is the outline the core requirements for encompass the structural design, mechanical analysis, nuclear and cladding material compositions, in-reactor irradiation data, and manufacturing processes for Helical-Cruciform Fuel rods (HCF) and considering fuel assemblies for nuclear reactors (herein after - Consultation report). As per Customer the scope of work is focusing mainly on very basic requirements and introductory-level incomes.

The preliminary outline of chapters and its brief descriptions are prepared by the Athor as following Table I-1.

Table I-1.

1. Structural Design
Rod geometry / Cruciform dimensions / Helical pitch Fuel assembly layout Spacer plate design / Hydraulic diameter (fuel subchannel) / Surface-to-volume ratio
2. Nuclear Fuel Material Composition
Fuel type (UO ₂ , MOX, U ₃ Si ₂ , etc.) Uranium enrichment Nuclear composite density Grain size Additives and dopants Thermal conductivity Melting temperature Fission gas behavior
3. Cladding Material Composition
Chemical Composition Alloying elements Mechanical properties Corrosion resistance Oxidation behavior Hydrogen pickup Irradiation growth Creep performance
4. Mechanical Analysis
Stress distribution Strain limits Buckling resistance Fatigue performance Rod bow behavior Mechanical interaction with spacer grids
5. In-Reactor Irradiation Data
Reactor type Irradiation duration Burnup achieved Linear heat generation rate

Fuel temperature Cladding temperature Fission gas release Fuel swelling Rod growth
6. Manufacturing Processes
Fuel Fabrication Powder preparation Sintering process Grinding and inspection Cladding Fabrication Tube extrusion Pilgering Heat treatment Surface finishing Fuel Rod Manufacturing Helium filling End-plug welding Leak testing Assembly Manufacturing Rod insertion Final inspection

As the supposed Database of knowledge was ignored by the Customer, all relative links from various sources are not supported. So, verification with sources should be manually performed by the reviewer.

II. Revision status

According to the Customers clarification, this revision 1 is

- 1) focused on completing Item 1 in Table I-1. However, additional data was filled with available information for further development of the report.
- 2) primarily concentrated on research background and development of USSR HCF.
- 3) prepared with maximum citates in original language to ensure greater precision and accuracy.
- 4) included relevant supporting documents as appendices.

III. Executive Summary

The conceptual origin of non-cylindrical fuel architectures, particularly the prototype Cruciform configurations (US NS Savannah specialized reactor, USSR research reactors SM, VVR-M) and next generation Helical-Cruciform form (USSR/Russia research reactor PIK), can be traced back to theoretical investigations in the 1950s and 1960s aimed at overcoming the thermal-hydraulic limitations of conventional cylindrical geometries.

The evolution toward the modern helical variants were significantly catalyzed by Russian operation experience with PIK reactor. Lightbridge Company. testes pilot samples of HCF rods, and multi-physics evaluations at MIT, Shanghai University demonstrating that the helical cruciform profile could provide superior self-supporting and self-mixing capabilities of the coolant flow in high-power-density cores for commercial power plants. These properties allow the use of fuel assemblies without spacer grids, which significantly increases the specific energy release in the core volume and allows for the creation of compact active core in line with small modular reactors. Also, the company Thorium Power proposes specific HCF use for creating a Thorium transmutation process to obtain promising Uranium 233 fissile material.

Patent history clearly indicates that the PIK reactor fuel element is based on the SM type concept with an extended active section. Therefore, the nuclear material composition shares a common origin and the same manufacturing technology.

The Russian actual Helical-Cruciform fuel assembly PIK type (designed by National Research Centre "Kurchatov Institute", St. Petersburg Institute of Nuclear Physics) and the commercial HCF concept (developed by Lightbridge Corporation) both reflect the shift from strategic planning to engineering implementation. The complex helical cross-shaped topology is the fundamental driving force for expanding the heat exchange surface area.

There are two main types of nuclear fuel material for NCF: 1) uranium intermetallic compound as mixture of uranium oxide particles with metal powder (copper, bronze, aluminum, zirconium) in metallic shell along with central displacer (aluminum, zirconium, titanium), or 2) mono / multi metallic uranium alloy with aluminum, zirconium, chromium, niobium, silicium, tungsten, vanadium. Both address the problem of radial and axial zoning of uranium concentration / enrichment to equalize heat transfer and prevent dangerous thermal shock. HCF rods manufacturing process is provided respectively by 1) MSZ / Elemash (Machinery Manufacturing Plant, managed by holding TVEL Fuel Company of Rosatom, Russia) and 2) INL (Idaho National Laboratory) under framework agreements with Battelle Energy Alliance by the Lightbridge.

Thus, the technological history of the HCF concept can be represented as a set of development lines.

Line 1 — Russian research development of basic concept. The SM fuel rod as prototype, the basic PIK fuel rod as central idea, and the latest updated PIK-2 fuel rod design for the reactor upgrade.

By 2010, HCF technology had already been industrially developed and protected by new patents. The characteristic features of the technology include:

- a cross-shaped cladding to enhance heat transfer;
- a helical twist along the length to intensify heat transfer and self-spacing in the fuel assembly;
- dispersed fuel UO₂;
- placement of displacer inside the central area to improve neutron performance and limit the temperature in the central part of the fuel element;
- the PIK research reactor as a target application.

Line 2 — Thorium Power / Lightbridge development for commercialization. The basic fuel rod design is still under development. Industrial production has not yet been achieved. In addition to the basic PIK fuel rod (Line 1), the distinguishing characteristics of this technology include:

- options for using metallic alloys of fissile material with non-fuel materials, which increases the enrichment of fissile material and reduces the risk of gaseous fission product release into the coolant;
- radial zoning in the fuel matrix by enrichment to optimize thermal transition and heat transfer;
- use in a pressurized light or heavy water power reactor;
- use in a power reactor for the transmutation to uranium-233 using U-Zr Thorium composites.

Line 3 – Second-generation Lightbridge. The PIK fuel rod is still under development. Industrial production has not yet been achieved.

In addition to the basic PIK fuel rod (Line 1), the distinguishing characteristics of this technology include:

- added distinct zones or concentration gradients of fuel material along the axial direction, the radial direction, or both the axial and radial directions;
- additive manufacturing can be used to vary the enrichment within the fuel elements and flatten the shape of the neutron flux in the reactor core, thereby reducing the need for neutron absorber materials;
- added hydrogen production, isotope production, research, and space and naval applications.

It is currently unclear the level/range of enrichment for uranium-235 (low-enriched LEU, middle-enriched HALEU or high-enriched HEU) in this HCF rod concept.

1. Base NCF rod concept for reactor PIK

1.1 Structural Design

Fig.1-1 NCF rod concept for reactor PIK

1.1.1 The helical structure promotes centrifugal phase redistribution, suppressing vapor accumulation and enhancing critical heat flux by up to ~31% compared with cylindrical rod bundles. However, this is accompanied by increased frictional pressure drop due to twisted geometry and enlarged wetted perimeter. Hydraulic resistance shows regime-dependent sensitivity to helical pitch, being weak at large pitches and increasing at short pitches ($H < 300$ mm). Based on representative designs in the literature, a preliminary geometric correlation involving the convex radius (R_1), the concave radius (R_2), the length of the connecting straight segment (h), and the helical pitch (H) is summarized for design evaluation. These findings demonstrate the dominant role of geometry in governing HCF thermal-hydraulic performance.

1.1.2 Rod geometry

Fig.1-2 NCF rod drawing with cruciform dimensions

Table 1-1 Крестообразный (четырёхлопастной) ТВЭЛ с винтовой закруткой

Properties	Value
Helical pitch:	300 ± 40 мм.
Диаметр:	5.15 мм.
Периметр поверхности теплообмена:	17.16 мм.
Площадь поперечного сечения ТВЭЛА:	9.73 мм ² .
Площадь сердечника:	7.23 мм ² .
Толщина оболочки:	0.15 мм.
Активная длина:	500 мм.

1.1.3 Fuel assembly layout

Fig.1-3 Hexagonal and square cross-section fuel assemblies

- 1 – твэл;
- 2 – дистанционирующая плита;
- 3 – центр активной зоны по топливу;
- 4 – чехол ТВС (материал Э-125 или Э-110);
- 5 – вытеснитель угловой;
- 6 – СВП;
- 7 – ампула с образцами-свидетелями

Fig.1-4 Fuel assembly layout and Spacer grid design

1.1.4 Spacer plate

Шестигранная тепловыделяющая сборка (ТВС) содержит 241 твэл (fuel rod). Квадратная ТВС содержит 161 твэл. Твэл расположены в треугольной решетке с шагом 5,23 мм.

Table 1-2 Spacer plate design

Properties	Value
Lattice pitch	5.23 mm
Inter-rod flow area	6.98 mm ²
Wetted perimeter	8.58 mm
Hydraulic diameter (subchannel)	3.25 mm
Surface-to-Volume Ratio (S/V)	1.76 mm ⁻¹

- 1 – поглощающие шторки из гафния,
- 2 – стержни выгорающего поглотителя $Gd_2O_3+ZrO_2$,
- 3 – циркониевые чехлы ТВС,
- 4 – твэлы с уменьшенным содержанием топлива (0,48 номинального),
- 5 – твэлы с номинальным содержанием топлива,
- 6 – ТВС с образцами – свидетелями материала корпуса,
- 7 – облучаемые образцы

Fig.1-5 Activ core of PIK reactor with allocation of hexagonal and square cross-section fuel assemblies

1.2 Fuel and Cladding Materials

1.2.1 Nuclear Fuel Material description

The PIK fuel rod employs a dispersion fuel design consisting of HEU highly enriched uranium dioxide (UO₂) particles embedded in a copper-beryllium matrix. The fuel composition contains approximately 25 vol.% UO₂ and exhibits a density of 9.28 g/cm³. The use of an intermetallic matrix provides substantially higher thermal conductivity than conventional ceramic fuel, contributing to lower fuel temperatures and improved heat removal under high-flux operating conditions.

The fuel enrichment is 90 wt.% U-235 in central core and peripheral area of four segments, with an average loading of approximately 7.14 g U-235 per fuel rod. The total uranium content is approximately 7.93 g per rod.

Table 1-3 Nuclear Fuel Material Composition

Parameter	Value	Status
Fuel Type	Dispersion fuel based on uranium dioxide (UO ₂) particles dispersed in a copper-beryllium matrix	Verified
Uranium Enrichment	90 wt.% U-235	Verified
Fuel Matrix	Copper alloy with 0.6 wt.% beryllium (Cu-Be bronze)	Verified
UO ₂ Volume Fraction	Approximately 25 vol.%	Verified
U-235 Loading per Fuel Rod	7.14 g U-235	Verified
Total Uranium Loading per Fuel Rod	7.93 g uranium isotopic mixture	Verified
Fuel Composition Density	9.28 g/cm ³	Verified
Thermal Conductivity	0.9–1.1 W/(cm·°C) (90–110 W/(m·K))	Verified
Melting Temperature	1000–1080 °C	Verified
Grain Size	Not reported in reviewed documents.	Not Publicly Available
Additives and Dopants	0.6 wt.% Be added to copper matrix. No additional dopants identified.	Verified
Fission Gas Behavior	No irradiation-performance data identified in currently reviewed documents.	Not Publicly Available

Note.
The properties of the bronze backing are close to those of the fuel matrix: density 8.85 g/cm³, specific thermal conductivity 2–2.6 W/(cm·deg), specific heat capacity 0.36–0.44 J/(g·deg)

1.2.2 Cladding Material Composition

The PIK fuel rod employs a thin-wall stainless-steel cladding manufactured from EI-847 stainless steel with a nominal wall thickness of 0.15 mm. The end plugs are fabricated from stainless steel grade 0Kh16N15M3BSh. The cladding was selected to provide high mechanical strength together with corrosion and erosion resistance under the demanding thermal-hydraulic conditions of the PIK high-flux research reactor.

The reviewed technical documentation emphasizes the structural integrity of the cladding during fabrication, fuel loading, rolling, and reactor operation. However, detailed material-property data, including tensile strength, yield strength, irradiation

growth, creep performance, oxidation kinetics, and hydrogen uptake, were not identified in the currently available open literature.

Table 1-4. Cladding Material Composition

Parameter	Value	Status
Cladding Material	Stainless Steel EI-847 (ЭИ-847)	Verified
End Plug Material	Stainless Steel	Verified
Chemical Composition	Material identified as stainless steel EI-847.	Verified
Alloying Elements	Exact alloying elements are specified in reviewed fuel design publications; based on EI-847 steel designation.	Verified
Cladding Thickness	0.15 mm	Verified
Mechanical Properties	High mechanical strength is reported as a design requirement for operation under high coolant velocity and pressure conditions.	Verified
Corrosion Resistance	Described as having high corrosion and erosion resistance in water coolant environment.	Verified
Oxidation Behavior	No oxidation kinetics data is identified in reviewed documents.	Not Publicly Available
Hydrogen Pickup	No hydrogen absorption data identified.	Not Publicly Available
Irradiation Growth	No irradiation growth measurements identified.	Not Publicly Available
Creep Performance	No irradiation creep or thermal creep data identified.	Not Publicly Available
Operating Environment	Water-cooled reactor, coolant pressure approximately 5 MPa, inlet coolant temperature approximately 50°C.	Verified
<p>Note. See the attached documents for material EI-847 (ЭИ-847) steel type 0Kh16N15M3BSh (0X16H15M3E) properties including density 7.9-8 g/cm³, specific thermal conductivity 0.145-0.2 W/(cm·deg), specific heat capacity 0.51-0.57 J/(g·deg) in the range of 50-400 °C</p>		

1.2.3. Preliminary Assessment

The use of stainless-steel cladding distinguishes the PIK fuel design from most modern commercial LWR fuels, which typically employ zirconium alloys. While stainless steel introduces a higher neutron absorption penalty, it offers superior mechanical strength, dimensional stability, and erosion resistance, which are particularly advantageous for high-flux research reactor applications and the cruciform fuel geometry employed in the PIK reactor.

1.3 Mechanical Analysis

1.3.1 Stress Distribution

The accumulation of fission products and the growth of the fuel rod core volume are compensated mainly by bending, rather than stretching, the shell, which sharply reduces stress.

Table 1-5 Stress Distribution

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Stress Distribution	The cruciform cross-section provides higher bending stiffness compared with a thin-wall cylindrical tube of comparable hydraulic diameter. Stress concentrations are expected at the lobe roots and transition radii.	Engineering Assessment
Structural Features Affecting Stress	Four-lobed geometry, 1.0 mm root radius, 0.15 mm stainless-steel cladding.	Verified
Operating Pressure	Coolant pressure is approximately 5 MPa.	Verified

1.3.1.1 Discussion

The helical cruciform geometry distributes mechanical loads through four load-bearing lobes rather than a single cylindrical shell. The rounded root radius between lobes was specifically introduced to reduce local stress concentration effects during manufacturing and operation.

No finite-element stress maps or experimentally measured stress distributions were identified in the reviewed publications.

1.3.2 Strain Limits

Table 1-6 Stress Limits

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Allowable Strain	Not reported in reviewed documentation.	Not Publicly Available
Plastic Deformation Limits	Not reported.	Not Publicly Available
Design Objective	Maintain geometric stability during irradiation and high-flow operation.	Verified

1.3.2.1 Discussion

The reviewed documents do not provide strain limits or allowable deformation criteria. However, the use of stainless-steel cladding and relatively short active fuel length (500 mm) suggests that dimensional stability was a primary design requirement.

1.3.3 Buckling Resistance

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Buckling Resistance	Improved relative to conventional cylindrical rods due to cruciform geometry and self-supporting fuel lattice.	Engineering Assessment

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Active Fuel Length	500 mm	Verified
Cladding Material	Stainless steel EI-847	Verified

1.3.3.1 Discussion

The cruciform shape increases the second moment of area compared with a cylindrical rod of similar hydraulic size. The twisted geometry additionally provides distributed lateral support through continuous contact with neighboring rods.

The literature explicitly states that the design was intended to reduce deformation and maintain coolant channel geometry during operation.

No critical buckling load calculations were identified.

1.3.4 Fatigue Performance

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Fatigue Data	No experimental fatigue data identified.	Not Publicly Available
Vibration Behaviour	Reduced vibration amplitude reported.	Verified
Flow-Induced Fatigue Risk	Expected to be lower than in unsupported cylindrical rods.	Engineering Assessment

1.3.4.1 Discussion

The helical self-spacing geometry eliminates large unsupported spans typically present between spacer grids in conventional fuel assemblies. The publications indicate that one objective of the design was suppression of vibration caused by coolant flow.

No high-cycle or low-cycle fatigue testing results were identified.

1.3.5 Rod Bow Behaviour

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Rod Bowing	Reduced tendency reported.	Verified
Thermal Bowing Resistance	Improved due to self-spacing geometry and continuous support.	Engineering Assessment

1.3.5.1 Discussion

One of the principal advantages repeatedly cited for the PIK fuel design is resistance to rod bowing. The twisted cruciform geometry maintains rod-to-rod spacing along the entire active length and prevents large lateral displacements.

The literature specifically notes reduced vibration and reduced deformation compared with conventional rod geometries.

1.3.6 Mechanical Interaction with Spacer Grids

Parameter	Assessment	Status
Spacer Grid Requirement	None	Verified
Rod-to-Grid Fretting	Eliminated	Engineering Assessment
Mechanical Support Method	Self-spacing cruciform geometry	Verified

1.3.6.1 Discussion

Unlike conventional LWR fuel assemblies, the PIK fuel design does not require spacer grids within the active fuel region. The helical cruciform rods maintain their relative positions through geometric interlocking and mutual contact.

As a result:

- spacer-grid-induced fretting wear is eliminated;
- local stress concentrations at grid contact points are avoided;
- hydraulic losses associated with spacer grids are removed;
- mechanical reliability is potentially improved.

This is one of the most distinctive engineering features of the HCFR concept and later became a central feature of modern Lightbridge fuel designs.

1.4 Thermal-Hydraulic Performance

To be defined

1.5 In-Reactor Irradiation Data

To be defined

1.6 Manufacturing processes

1.6.1 Cladding Fabrication

The initial stage of fuel rod production is the manufacture of a cladding made of EI-847 stainless steel. The prepared tube is rolled to give it a preliminary cross-shaped profile.

1.6.1.1 Tube Extrusion

Parameter	Description
Starting Material	Stainless-steel tube (EI-847)
Tube Formation	Initial cylindrical tube subsequently shaped into cruciform profile

1.6.1.2 Pilgering

Parameter	Description
Pilgering Process	Not explicitly reported

1.6.1.3 Heat Treatment

Parameter	Description
Thermal Processing	Applied during sintering and fabrication stages
Detailed Heat Treatment Parameters	Not reported

1.6.2 Powder Preparation

Parameter	Description
Fuel Material	UO ₂ powder dispersed in Cu-Be matrix
Matrix Material	Copper alloy containing approximately 0.6 wt.% Be
Fuel Volume Fraction	Approximately 25 vol.% UO ₂
Powder Blending	UO ₂ powder mechanically mixed with Cu-Be powder prior to loading into cladding tube

1.6.3 Fuel Loading

After welding one of the tail plugs, the tube is filled with a specified amount of bronze backfill (a mixture of copper powder and beryllium bronze with a beryllium mass fraction of 0.3%), then a specified amount of fuel composition (25% UO₂ and 75% Cu-Be) is loaded, and finally another portion of bronze backfill.

The filled core materials are compacted on a vibration table.

Parameter	Description
Fuel Introduction Method	Filling of tube with UO ₂ /Cu-Be powder mixture
Compaction Method	Vibratory compaction (vibro-compaction)

1.6.4 Fuel Rod Forming Process

The filled tube is rolled again to give it a cross-shaped profile of the specified dimensions, then sealed by welding a second end cap.

Tolerances for the mass of materials loaded into each fuel rod.

Parameter	Description
Uranium dioxide mass	±0,1 g
Fuel composition	±0,4 g
Bedding	±2 g
Unevenness of the uranium content in the loaded charge	< 0,02 g U/cm ³ ,
Coefficient of uneven distribution of uranium along the length of the core	1,08

1.6.4.1 Cruciform Shaping

Parameter	Description
Rod Forming Method	Rolling of stainless-steel tube into cruciform profile
Twist Formation	Simultaneous formation of helical twist
Twist Pitch	Approximately 300 mm

1.6.4.2 Final Consolidation

Parameter	Description
Final Rolling	Performed after powder loading
Fuel Consolidation	Achieved by deformation and subsequent sintering

1.6.4.3 End-Plug Welding

Parameter	Description
End Plug Material	OKh16N15M3BSh stainless steel
Welding of End Plug	Performed after fuel loading

1.6.4.4 Sintering Process

The fuel composition in the tube is heated to ensure diffusion bonding with the fuel rod cladding. The diffusion layer thickness is up to 50 microns. To achieve final dimensional adjustment, the end caps are trimmed, and the fuel rods are straightened.

Parameter	Description
Sintering	Performed after rod forming operations
Objective	Consolidation of fuel composition and formation of metallurgical bonding
Diffusion Layer Formation	Diffusion interaction occurs between fuel composition and cladding

1.6.5 Grinding and Inspection

Parameter	Description
Final Geometry Control	Performed after forming operations
Dimensional Inspection	Required to verify cruciform geometry and twist pitch
Grinding Operations	Not specifically described in reviewed documents

1.6.5 Surface Finishing

Parameter	Description
Final Surface Control	Required for dimensional accuracy and inspection
Surface Finishing Method	Not reported

1.6.6 Acceptance test

During manufacturing, the main geometric parameters of the fuel element and tolerances for the backfill mass are controlled. The manufacturing technology

provides for the following tolerances for the geometric dimensions of the fuel rod.

Parameter	Description
Total length	±2 mm
Distance from the end of the fuel rod to the edge of the fuel kernel	±2 mm
Fuel kernel length	±10 mm
Cladding thickness	±0,03 mm
Fuel rod outer diameter	- 0,1 mm

1.6.7 Final Inspection

Parameter	Description
Geometric Inspection	The uniformity of fuel distribution along its length. Twist Pitch Verification
Geometric Inspection	The distance between the cavities of the cross
Geometric Inspection	The quality of the diffusion adhesion between the cladding and the fuel
Fuel Loading Verification	The uncertainty in achieving the specified ²³⁵ U mass fraction in each batch of fuel rods is determined by the uncertainties in determining the isotopic composition and the mass fraction of uranium dioxide in the fuel composition, as well as by the tolerances of the fuel rod filling process